

“Impact of Stress Level among Married Working Women with Special Reference to Chennai City”

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Abstract

In the present study, an effort has been made to identify and reveal the impact of stress level among married working women with special reference to Chennai city. Data were collected from a sample of 50 married working women through personal interview, using simple random sampling method. Descriptive analysis and inferential statistics are used to analyse the data. The study used percentage analysis, chi-square test, one way ANOVA, t- test method to determine the relationship between demographic characteristics and impact of stress level among married working women. Working women still do majority of childcare and domestic work and lack of flexible working provision and long-hours of working culture disadvantage more women than men, as they will be unable to put in the hours required to advance their careers. The main findings of the study show that all the respondents have stress due to personal and workplace related problems-like managing the daily home activities, child care and looking after the family members. These are the major factors which cause stress among the married working women. Thus the study reveals the cause and impact of stress among the married working women and to take initiatives on more research, on different aspects mentioned, to improve the work-life balance among married working women to explore their potential to the maximum extends.

Keywords: Married working women, stress, Domestic work, Causes, Work life balance, Careers, Work place.

Needs for the Study

Now-a-day's financial independence is the ability to earn one's own living, including women. In India, most women are efficient home-makers and their careers take a back seat when they enter into motherhood. Women's domestic need always overcome their career goals. For example during maternity periods, most of the women break their career.

Scope of the Study

Married working women are engaged in dual role, as home maker and career builder. Support should be given by society and family member's to alleviate the job stress of married working women, so that they can maintain their quality of life and adjust with family members and workmates. The dual responsibility of home and work,

calls for multiple roles, which put greater strain on married working women. Researches comparing the stress level of married working women are also scanty. Therefore, there is a need to conduct a detailed study on stresses among married working women in this direction, and hence the present study on “Impact of stress level among married working women with special reference to Chennai city” is undertaken.

Objectives of the Study

The study attempts to address the following key research objectives:

- To identify the causes for stress among married working women.
- To determine the impact of stress level on married working women.
- To find out activities done for relieving the stress among married working women.
- To analyse difference between work situation and personal life.

Research Methodology

Descriptive analysis and inferential statistics are used to analyse the data among married working women with special reference to Chennai city. The number of respondents restricted for the study is 50. The area where the data collected is Chennai city. The respondents are the women who reside in Chennai city. In this simple random sampling method was used to collect the data. The present study was collected through a personalized interview method with the female respondents.

Review of Related Literatures

Muntazir Maqbool Kermene (2016) has presented a paper “A psychological study on stress among employed women and housewives and its management through Progressive Muscular Relaxation Technique (PMRT) and mindfulness breathing”. The study aims to assess the stress level among the employed women and house wives. In this research 100 samples are taken from working (50) and non working (50) women. Results reveal that the stress level was high among the employed women than the house wives.

Vemuri Swathi and M. Sudhir Reddy (2016) “Stress among working women”. The main aim of the study is to find our stress level among women and the causes of stress among working women. The results indicate that the working women generally involved simultaneously in many tasks, juggling between family and work responsibilities, which leads towards stress among them.

Kanta Devi (2016) conducted a study on “Level of stress among working and non-working women in Chandigarh”. This study was to compare the level of stress and association among working and non-working women. The study revealed that the stress level was higher in non-working women as compared to working women.

T.Narayana Rao and Dr. V. Srinivasa Prasad (2015) has examined “An impact of stress on women employees with reference to selected BPO’s Visakhaptnam”. This study highlights the critical need to investigate the stress for women workers in the BPO industry. The finding of the study was that, majority of the women employees feel pessimistic about their job and they ranked it as number 1. The study reveals that 23% of the women employees are facing multiple health issues like -Frequent Headaches and back pains and 26% of the married women are facing child care problems.

Anil kumar and meenakshi yadav (2015) presented a paper on “Occupational stress among working women-an experience wise analysis”. This paper aims to examine occupational stress among working women. The findings of the results was that the working women having less experience faced the stress relatively more as compared to working women having higher level of experience.

Statistical Tools**One Way Anova**

Ho: There is no significant difference between the age of the respondent and causes of stress.

H1: There is significant difference between the age of the respondent and causes of stress.

Table showing relationship between age of the respondent and causes of stress

Factors	Strongly agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
Long working hours	40	4	2	2	2
Heavy workload	16	26	4	2	2
Job insecurity	20	16	7	2	5
Harassment	15	19	11	3	2
Changes in duties	11	16	16	2	5

One way ANOVA table (Long working hours)

Sources of variance	Sum of squares	Degree of freedom	Mean sum of squares	F value	Significance value
Between group	.382	3	.127	0.505	0.681
Within group	11.618	46	.253	-	-
Total	12.000	49	-	-	-

$F = \text{Between group mean sum of squares} / \text{Within group mean sum of squares}$

$F = 0.505$

Significant value = 0.681

Table value of F at 5% level of significance at (3, 46) degree of freedom is 2.76.

Table value = 2.76

Calculated value = 0.681

Interpretation: It is observed from the above table the calculated value of significant is lower than the table value at 5% level of significance, so the null hypothesis is accepted. There is no significant difference among the mean, thus there is no significant influence of age and long working hours among married working women.

One way ANOVA table (Heavy workload)

Sources of variance	Sum of squares	Degree of freedom	Mean sum of squares	F value	Significance value
Between group	12.448	3	4.149	5.381	0.003
Within group	35.472	46	.771	-	-
Total	47.920	49	-	-	-

$F = \text{Between group mean sum of squares} / \text{Within group mean sum of squares}$

$F = 5.381$

Significant value = 0.003

Table value of F at 5% level of significance at (3, 46) degree of freedom is 2.76.

Table value = 2.76

Calculated value = 0.003

Interpretation: It is observed from the above table the calculated value of significant is lower than the table value at 5% level of significance, so the null hypothesis is accepted. There is no significant difference among the mean, thus there is no significant influence of age and heavy workload among married working women.

t-TEST

Ho: There is no significant difference between the occupations of the respondents and impact of physiological and psychological stress among married working women.

H1: There is significant difference between the occupations of the respondents and impact of physiological and psychological stress among married working women.

Table showing relationship between Occupations of the respondents and Impact of physiological and psychological stress

Factors	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
Headaches	29	13	5	1	2
Nervousness	12	22	11	2	3
Sleeping difficulties	20	13	11	3	3
Depression	16	13	8	7	6
Irritability	15	19	11	3	2

Independent samples test (t-test table)

Headaches	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference
Equal variances assumed	-1.513	34	.139	-.64286	.42481
Equal variances not assumed	-1.009	7.821	.343	-.64286	.63717

Table value of t at 5% level of significance at 34 degree of freedom is 1.645

Table value = 1.645 Calculated value = 0.139

Interpretation: It shows from the above test the calculated value of t is lower than the table value at 5% level of significance, so the null hypothesis is accepted. There is no significant difference among the mean, thus there is no significant influence of occupations of the respondents and headaches among married working women.

Independent samples test (t-test table)

Nervousness	t	Df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference
Equal variances assumed	.579	34	.566	.17857	.30829
Equal variances not assumed	.586	11.533	.569	.17857	.30452

Table value of t at 5% level of significance at 34 degree of freedom is 1.645

Table value = 1.645 Calculated value = 0.566

Interpretation: It shows from the above test the calculated value of t is lower than the table value at 5% level of significance, so the null hypothesis is accepted. There is no significant difference among the mean, thus there is no significant influence of occupations of the respondents and nervousness among married working women.

Independent samples test (t-test table)

Sleeping difficulties	t	Df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference
Equal variances assumed	.516	34	.609	.21429	.41517
Equal variances not assumed	.411	8.839	.691	.21429	.52101

Table value of t at 5% level of significance at 34 degree of freedom is 1.645

Table value = 1.645 Calculated value = 0.609

Interpretation: It shows from the above test the calculated value of t is lower than the table value at 5% level of significance, so the null hypothesis is accepted. There is no significant difference among the mean, thus there is no significant influence of occupations of the respondents and sleeping difficulties among married working women.

Independent samples test (t-test table)

Depression	t	Df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference
Equal variances assumed	-1.675	34	.103	-.85714	.51186
Equal variances not assumed	-1.349	8.918	.211	-.85714	.63561

Table value of t at 5% level of significance at 34 degree of freedom is 1.645

Table value = 1.645 Calculated value = 0.103

Interpretation: It shows from the above test the calculated value of t is lower than the table value at 5% level of significance, so the null hypothesis is accepted. There is no significant difference among the mean, thus there is no significant influence of occupations of the respondents and depression among married working women.

Independent samples test (t-test table)

Irritability	t	Df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference
Equal variances assumed	.179	34	.859	.07143	.39857
Equal variances not assumed	.271	28.330	.788	.07143	.26316

Table value of t at 5% level of significance at 34 degree of freedom is 1.645

Table value = 1.645 Calculated value = 0.859

Interpretation: It shows from the above test the calculated value of t is lower than the table value at 5% level of significance, so the null hypothesis is accepted. There is no significant difference among the mean, thus there is no significant influence of occupations of the respondents and irritability among married working women.

Chi – Square Test

Ho: There is no significant difference between the qualifications and activities done for relieving from stress.

H1: There is significant difference between the qualifications and activities done for relieving from stress.

Table showing relationship between qualifications of the respondents and activities done for relieving from stress

Factors	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
Regular exercise	43	2	2	2	1
Meditation / Yoga / Massage	9	34	2	3	2
Adequate sleep	12	28	6	2	2
Spending time with beloved ones	20	13	11	3	3
Going out	12	25	9	2	2

Chi-Square Tests Table

Regular exercise	Value	Df	Assumption. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	23.827a	9	.005
Likelihood Ratio	18.246	9	.032
Linear-by-Linear Association N of Valid Cases	4.649 50	1	.031

Table value = 16.919 calculated value = 0.005

Interpretation: It is observed from the above table the value of chi square at 5% level of significance at 9 Degree of freedom is 16.919. As the calculated value is less than the table value, null hypothesis is accepted at 5% level of significance. Thus it is concluded that there is a no significant difference between qualification and regular exercise among married working women.

Chi-Square Tests Table

Meditation / Yoga / Massage	Value	Df	Assumption. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	23.581a	12	.023
Likelihood Ratio	20.984	12	.051
Linear-by-Linear Association N of Valid Cases	4.598 50	1	.032

Table value = 21.026 calculated value = 0.023

Interpretation: It is observed from the above table the value of chi square at 5% level of significance at 12 Degree of freedom is 21.026. As the calculated value is less than the table value, null hypothesis is accepted at 5% level of significance. Thus it is concluded that there is a no significant difference between qualification and meditation/yoga/massage among married working women.

Chi-Square Tests Table

Adequate sleep	Value	Df	Assumption. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	21.928a	9	.009
Likelihood Ratio	27.231	9	.001
Linear-by-Linear Association N of Valid Cases	.675 50	1	.411

Table value = 16.919 calculated value = 0.009

Interpretation: It is observed from the above table the value of chi square at 5% level of significance at 9 Degree of freedom is 16.919. As the calculated value is less than the table value, null hypothesis is accepted at 5% level of significance. Thus it is concluded that there is a no significant difference between qualification and regular adequate sleep among married working women.

Chi-Square Tests Table

Spending time with beloved ones	Value	Df	Assumption. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	5.750a	6	.452
Likelihood Ratio	6.980	6	.323
Linear-by-Linear Association N of Valid Cases	2.393 50	1	.122

Table value = 12.592 calculated value = 0.452

Interpretation: It is observed from the above table the value of chi square at 5% level of significance at 6 Degree of freedom is 12.592. As the calculated value is less than the table value, null hypothesis is accepted at 5% level of significance. Thus it is concluded that there is a no significant difference between qualification and spending time with beloved ones among married working women.

Chi-Square Tests Table

Going out	Value	Df	Assumption. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	16.486a	9	.057
Likelihood Ratio	15.614	9	.075
Linear-by-Linear Association	2.879	1	.090
N of Valid Cases	50		

Table value = 16.919 calculated value = 0.057

Interpretation: It is observed from the above table the value of chi square at 5% level of significance at 9 Degree of freedom is 16.919. As the calculated value is less than the table value, null hypothesis is accepted at 5% level of significance. Thus it is concluded that there is a no significant difference between qualification and going out among married working women.

Findings

- Majority (68%) of the respondents are in the age group of 20-30 years followed by (16%) in the age group of 31-40 years. This indicates more respondents are below 30 years of age.
- Maximum (48%) of the married working women are under graduate (UG) followed by (22%) of post graduate (PG). This reveals that the majority of the respondents are under graduates.
- On the basis of the educational qualification, majority (56%) of the respondents are private concern employees followed by (18%) of government employees and the rest (13%) are self employees and other people. Here private concern employees are major part in the research.
- On the basis of the nature of job maximum (52%) of the respondents are on temporary job and the minimum (48%) of the married working women are having permanent job. This indicates majority of the respondents are having temporary job.
- Majority (42%) of the respondents monthly earnings was Rs.10,000 – 20,000, followed by (20%) of the respondents in the income range of up to Rs.20,001 – 30,000.
- On the basis of the causes of stress among married working women,
 - It is evident that a majority (60%) of the respondents indicated job insecurity factor was strongly agree that these factors lead to increased stress levels among married working women.
- The impact of physiological and psychological stress among married working women manifest itself on:
 - This indicates most of the people (58%) of the respondent reveals headaches and depression factor was strongly agree that these factors leads to high stress level.
- On the basis of the activities done for relieving from stress among married working women,
 - (56%) opted for physical exercise and (40%) opted for spending time with beloved ones and both categories strongly agree that these factors can help to reduce stress level among married working women.

Suggestions

- Planning the work is one of the main stress reliving activities, which can reduce the stress from the life. If any work either in work place or in the home, women will have to plan the work according to their schedule.

- Managing the time between family life and work life is to finish their work life within given time and to spare rest of time to manage family.
- Married working women should go to bed at roughly the same time each day, so that their mind and body get used to a predictable bedtime routine, resulting in getting up reliving from stress. Women lose energy in both in work place and in home while doing home work and the above said routine helps to bring out the best in them.
- Regular physical activity (exercise) will also improve the quality of the sleep and it will give healthy life to married working women.
- Regular interactions with friends, relatives, neighbors, work colleague, or even a trained professional, can help to reduce stress level and find the solution for women's stress.
- Going out with family or friends can also lead to reduced stress level and that will give stress free life for married working women.
- The married working women should maintain regular diet, which will overcome the stress.
- They should take rest if sick. If feeling unwell, they should not feel that they have to carry on regardless. A short spell of rest will enable the body to recover faster. So regular rest must be considered as very important tool to reduce stress.

Conclusion

The present study title "Impact of stress among married working women" was conducted with 50 sample respondents. The main findings of the study show that all the respondents have stress due to personal and workplace sources of problems, like managing the daily home activities, child care and looking after the family members. These are the major factors which cause stress among the married working women. Stress will lead to the headaches, nervousness, fatigue, sleeping difficulties, dermatological issues, depression, anxiety, discouragement, irritability, cognitive difficulties. The poor relationship with superior and colleagues in a workplace creates an obstacle for achieving potential success. Thus the study reveals cause and impact of stress among the married working women. Hence initiative should be taken to do more research on different aspects discussed above, to improve work-life balance among married working women, enabling them to explore their potential to the maximum extends.

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